

CORRUPTION IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN NIGERIA: THE WAY FORWARD

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Abstract

Every tertiary institution is established to develop the nation. The tertiary education institutions is to transmit and acquire knowledge, experience and skills that will result in positive changes both in the individual and the society at large. The tertiary institution is geared toward providing a favourable environment for the upbringing of future leaders who will in turn provide solutions to socioeconomic and political issues of a nation. Corruption has eaten deep into tertiary institutions in Nigeria and has adversely affected the resources for the upliftment of tertiary institutions. In Nigerian tertiary institutions, corruption has destructively affected the entire system. Corruption has reduced the quality of education. Corruption which is not in line as regards the UNESCO universal idea of education for everybody abuses commitment to service but promotes shortcuts and unhealthy moves to much achievement. This paper focuses on corruption and how corruption has negatively affected tertiary institutions in Nigeria and suggests the way forward to eradicate the effect of corruption.

Keywords: Corruption, tertiary institutions and tackling corruption.

Introduction

The means of transmitting and acquiring knowledge, experience and skills that lead to positive changes in individuals and society is education. Ukata (2019) notes that such good qualities like honesty, selflessness, tolerance, devotion, hard effort and personal integrity are some of the traits and ideologies that education encourages at all levels. Education provides a favourable environment that encourages the raising of future leaders who will in turn provide solutions to social and economic challenges. The goal of education is to ensure that people are made to be sensible, cooperative, enlightened and follow the rules and regulations of the society. Education refers to the general aspect that involves the act of training, learning specialized abilities, information, behaviours and morals that are required for someone to be responsible in adding to social improvement with the understanding of the right and wrong which corruption may be a difficulty for. (Madaki, 2019).

The tertiary institutions are the last cader of educational teaching and learning. It is the peak of all levels of education. The tertiary institutions which include the universities, polytechnics and colleges should be a place of sanity, purity and of a great standard. Nevertheless, corruption has come in a provocative level. Corruption is the abuse of public power for personal gain and the wide range of illegal activities, such as bribery, extortion, fraud, nepotism, grafting, theft, embezzlement, falsifying academic transcripts, kickbacks and influence peddling. The destructive nature of corruption in the tertiary institutions has negatively affected the standard of education, hinder the productivity of future leaders and thus should be properly tackled.

Corruption: The basic instrument of destruction that is capable of characterizing individuals, system, institutions and the society in the negative is corruption. It is a wrong attitude, wrong conduct, the wrong practice, wrong policy, the wrong implementation of policy, etc. Corruption has been seen by different authors in diverse perspectives. The independent and corrupt practices commission (ICPC) defines corruption as bribery, fraud and other related offences (Eshemitan, 2015).

Anti-corruption Academy of Nigeria, 2017 notes that corruption occurs when public officials knowingly solicit or demand bribes or when private actors actively pay bribes to get around laws and procedures for business or competitive advantage in Nigeria, the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC) sees corruption as a non-aggressive, illegal and illegitimate behaviour by organizations and individuals that stimulate or provide illegal riches (Oladele, 2019) . The wrong use of official position or personal gain is corruption. It is any form of unethical and illegal action. The three components which include education are present in corrupt public office practices: (1) The activity must violate a law, rule, regulation or ethical standard; (2) It must include abusing the officer's position of authority; and (3) The reward must be money or anything of value to be measured in money.

According to Ofoezilem (2020) corruption refers to any action or inaction of any person, or group (public or private) deliberately perpetrated to secure advantages of one's relation, association or groups in a manner that detract from the acceptable, regulations, morals and/or ethical standards or code hence constituting a travesty of justice, equity and fair play. Corruption is the perversion of integrity or state of affairs through bribery, favour or moral depravity. Corruption normally happens when two parties have interacted to change the structure or process of society or the behaviour of functionaries in order to produce dishonest, unfaithful or undefiled situation.

Corruption transcends bribery, but includes treasury looting, and the deliberate bending of rules of the system to favour friends or hurt foes. It is expressly an absent of accountability, law and order (Ottite, 2021).

Emanating from the above discussion, corruption could be explained as an act that deviates from the formal rules, norms and laws of conduct governing the actions of someone in a position of private and public authority because of personal and private motives of ill-gotten wealth, power or status. It could as well be considered as an official judiciary person who unlawfully or wrongfully uses this situation or character to enrich himself or for another person, contrary to the rights and duty of others. Adelokun (2015) stressed that corruption manifest from the government to the governed, from doctors to their patients, from teachers to the students, from clergies to their congregation, from parents to their children, from transport operators to their clients, from bankers/banks to their customers, from security chiefs to their subordinates, from prison-officials to the prisoners, from global system of mobile communication operations to their subscribers, from judges to litigants, from lawyers to their clients, from employers to their employees and extreme anxiety. From the inception, corruption has become widespread, creating an enabling environment for organized crimes and bad governance, especially in the education sector that has without argument become corrosive.

Corruption in Education Sector

Education in every nation is aimed at bringing development and solving the various challenges in the society. The youths who are leaders of the future are nurtured and prepared through the educational system. Nevertheless, the aim of education is destroyed as a result of corruption in the educational system. Corruption in Nigeria's education has damaged the system so much that it has affected the standard of education; lack of adequate classrooms, lack of offices for working staff, conflict between staff unions and management of tertiary institutions, the high level of examination malpractices, ineffective teaching staff, the high level of extortions, etc.

Developing nations like Nigeria and others have corruption in every sector of economy, health, business, administrative and educational sectors. Concerning educational sector, Adelokun (2015) noted that corruption flows like a river of destructive waters. A peculiar consideration of the educational sector in Nigeria demonstrates that all levels are submerged into corruption: from the first level which is the primary level through the second level which is the secondary level and to the tertiary level which is the final level of education, sharp practices are the rules rather than the exception. This shows the obvious facts that Nigeria has failed to enjoy the merits of education

after 64 years of independence. Osai (2012) noted that the socio-political and economic development of a nation is in several ways determined by the quality and the level of educational attainment of its citizens. Education is actually the bedrock of modern civilization since: (a) The sector produces the future leaders who would take the nation to the much-needed technological breakthrough (b) It is during the training that characters and attributes are molded. It is said that the character of an individual is that of the gene (inherited) and the environment.

Mbu and Nwaduwa, (2023) see that while corruption in general has relieved a great deal of attention, corruption in education replaces good values and moral with a cynical view of the world when young and highly impressionable students learn that fighting corruption does not pay off but siding with it might not be seen as offensive. Mbu and Nwabuwa (2023) also notice classroom corruption. Classroom corruption emerged from the outright neglect which leads to inadequate fund availability, inadequate teaching aids and lack of good classroom, lack of proper numbering and the acute insufficiency of good teaching staff. Classroom corruption becomes worst when the teacher practically develops the following behaviours; lateness to classroom activities, inability to have proper classroom control during teaching, forcing learners to buy learning materials such as books, handout, etc, money for scores, sex for scores, examination malpractice, teaching out of context (not following the course content), lack of dedication, punctuality and regularity, paying of lip-service to the teaching job with giving more time and energy to other businesses, depriving students from critical thinking that encourages intellectual empowerment and not adopting student centered approach in teaching.

Tertiary Education in Nigeria

Educational system in Nigeria including other nations of the world is not under one level but different levels. Basically, there is the primary level, the secondary level, and the tertiary level. The tertiary level is the highest level of education where students/learners are trained both in character and in learning. The training in character and in learning is to ensure that tomorrow's leaders are adequately prepared to ensure good governance and development of the nation. The tertiary institution finally prepares the students in their respective disciplines/fields and study.

Tertiary level of education refers to the kind of education that someone attends when the main secondary level of education is over. It could be in a University, Polytechnic and Colleges. Tertiary education is post-secondary which comes after the secondary level of education and it is at this level that students focus in their area of specialization which is the core area of their pursuits. It could be sciences, arts and vocational studies (Johnstone, Arora & Experton, 1998).

Tertiary education is established towards enabling the students' preparation to job and learning special theories and important experiences. The tertiary institution's curriculum has been changed so that learners can resolve with ease as they meet with difficulties at workplaces.

According to Mgboji et al (2023), in the past, tertiary education was basically government-empowered but with the establishment of private universities, a lot of successes on the qualitative nature of education in tertiary institution which involved competition amongst the various graduating students. In some private universities like Babcock University and others, they have demonstrated stability including making effort to excel in educational improvement with an outcome that emanated a ranking website called webometric ranking and Times Higher Education ranking (Mbu, 2019). An observation in the developed nations shows that the high cost of tertiary education is very much pronounced and the awarding of scholarship to downplay the effect but in developing nations such as Nigeria, it is the government in power that has the administrative responsibility to own and take care of education in tertiary institutions. This has increasingly resulted to a situation where there is falling standard in education and also contributed to the turning out of unqualified graduates in many instances (Asiyai, 2014).

Tertiary Institutions and Corruption

In the current state of Nigeria tertiary institutions, corruption has become a household name. There is hardly any of the tertiary institutions that is devoid of corruption thus, corruption is closely associated with Nigerian tertiary institutions. This corruption ranges from the students to teaching and non-teaching staff, from the government to the tertiary institutions, from the tertiary institution administration to the staff and students. The list is inexhaustible. The rate of corruption in tertiary institutions is very alarming.

Mgboji et al (2023) further state that as previously said, corruption has negatively affected the numerous educational aspects worldwide and tertiary institutions inclusive. Corruption has been pronounced because in the various institutions of learning, both staff and students are observed of using their respective offices, positions and students' nature for private satisfaction and aggrandizement. They conduct many forms of negative acts for monetary reasons, sex, grades, admissions, promotions and empowering self, (Ololube, 2016). This ugly situation has destroyed several educational aspects. For example, a student who graduates with a first class instead of second class lower after sorting and paying his way through in the examination unit. This kind of students cannot operate as a first class graduate with a high level of intelligent as expected.

ted. There are situations where graduates will not be able to defend their certificates (Orji, Madu & Nwachukwu, 2012).

Nature of Corruption in Tertiary Institutions

Tertiary institutions in Nigeria have various natures of corruption since it is not restricted to a particular sector in the tertiary institutions. The spread of corruption within the various sectors of the tertiary institutions in Nigeria is on the high side. It is against this background that Mgboji et al (2023) further analyze the fact that there are different natures of corruption in Nigeria's tertiary institutions. In this paper, the following natures of corruption are explained. They include:

1) **Inducement of Teacher:** A teacher refers to anyone who has the responsibility in making students to become the exert reflection of themselves (Careerexplorer, 2019). The teacher refers to the medium for impartation of understanding and encouraging personnel based on their set skills in their different fields of study. The teacher has serious influence on the way learners relate to others in the present and in the future. Dennison (2019) in his submission stresses that a good teacher must be an expert in communication, engages students, be an excellent listener and also act in time with the expectation of all the numerous learners. In addition, teachers are always selfless and operate in the absence of favoritism and fear with the basic goal of making sure of the fact that the learner becomes an asset in his home and environment. Teacher inducement is an instance where a teacher or lecturer operates under the influence to act contrary against the accepted practice. This act of inducement could be initiated by a parent, a student or a colleague in exchange to buying scores, position and merits that are unexpected. Waite and Allen (2003), explain that the improper inducements are incorporated in ensuring that the corruptive nature and the falsely gotten wealth are achieved. This corrupt practice covers from fund stealing, sex, to traveling abroad among others. Teachers are quickly bribed because of their low financial standing in the society. The parents even go to the extent of sending a teaching staff including family members abroad, which is mostly very tempting for the teachers. In another dimension, the students or learners could subject the teacher through providing unrequested sex in order to achieve their ulterior motives. If they are unable to directly subject the teacher, they resort to involving the teacher's colleagues who can do the bidding with the concept of brotherhood meaning that the request must be met at any cost.

2) **Alteration of Result:** Results are end products of examination. It is the compilation of the various learning experiences of the students (Chimere, 2012). Chimere also states that students' results /learning outcome could be produced in two ways; either in hard or soft copy. The result of the student should showcase the actual learning experiences of the students and should not be

connected with any human alteration or manipulation. As the year goes by alteration of results becomes a major point of corruption in tertiary institutions. As a result of much over-dependence on the paper qualification instead of brilliance, students also do all they can to get excellent results no matter the cost. For this to be actualized, students consult with unreliable teaching staff who admit to render assistance by altering their results for an agreed fund (Kirya, 2019). If they don't succeed at the departments, they proceed to the examinations unit that takes care of computation and try to bribe through. Sometimes, the unfaithful staff who have positioned their agents send them out to get clients/students that are willing to do business with them. In case they are unsuccessful, they move to staff who are in charge of transcript management to secure their intention in altering result but they encounter with disappointment as the admitting institution requires the transcript to ascertain the results (Gilman, 1999).

3. Project Handling: Handling of projects takes place in all the tertiary institutions in Nigeria. It may be classroom construction, road maintenance, office construction or reconstruction job from commencement to the finishing point. These types of projects are identified because of real quotation and the requirement is that such contracts should remove some of the challenges of workers and students. The contractors over the period leave the job unattended to or leave without implementing the contract in all (Iyayi, 2010). Again, some projects that are of great benefit to improving the institution are mostly not attended to and contracts which are of benefit to the officers concerned are quickly approved and the required assistance are given. This is really a big challenge. For instance an institution of learning may encounter a challenge of unpaid salaries and road renovation but will outrageously provide amount to implement a project or raise a different project for themselves, their supporters or followers (Torulagha, 2013).

4) Fund Mismanagement: The act of mismanagement of fund is entirely the administrative action and responsibility that intentionally spend fund provided for someone in such a method which seen and described as falsely or deceitfully done (Ololube, 2016). Mismanagement of fund is a deliberate or unlawful act where unauthorized finance is use for diverted purposes specifically by personnel in public offices (Mestry, 2004). Most of the tertiary institutions in Nigeria have access subventions when the government in power that has the sole sponsorship responsibility and others generate funds from tuition but other financial payment are made by the students. There have been some cases about ways that the finance are spent, there are noted instances of wrong provision and how the funds are being managed. Some of the institutions of high learning have noted challenges and a stop in their performance as the fund have finished and improper supervision is carried out, the result shows how the funds are not utilized and this improper use

can be linked to the senior administrative officers or senior officers in the accounting department. As said before, corruption has gone deep into the fabrics of various sectors universally and higher institutions of learning are inclusive. Corruption has been very pronounced that workers (staff) and learners in these institutions of learning are seen to have utilized their offices and positions as students for personal reasons and aggrandizement. They encourage many kinds of negative acts for monetary reason, sexual acts, positions, admissions and promotions (Ololube, 2016). This situation has negatively influenced almost everyone and the wrong effect is reflecting in and outside the school environment. In nations that are developed, this corrupt practices are punished according to law but developing nations, such as Nigeria, handle corrupt practices with mild smiles and thus supporting corruption. Other instances of wrong use of finance also involved regular trips, commencing contract jobs without planning of completing them, the purchase of cars which may not be relevant at the time and having flamboyant way of living.

5. **Contract Inflation:** Cases of inflating contracts are great corruption process in Nigeria. Contractors are called in to compete and select contracts but the contract is given to the contractor who cut corners and pay the people concerned. The contractors are urged to shoot up the cost of the job without any form of consideration in as much as the agreed deal is actualized (Kirya, 2019). An instance is when, a job that should not go beyond 15 million naira goes up to 20 Million naira and in several situations, the fund is completely disbursed but partially carried out and are sometimes abandoned. The team whose responsibility is to assured the quality of the job are regularly bribed and becomes stagnated in doing things to abstain from being revealed and not to be sacked from job. Another very sad situation is awarding contracts to lots of unregistered companies. A printing press which is may not be fully registered can be given the opportunity to provide for computer items and when this kind of irregularity is not handled, corruption persists.

6. **Staff Recruitment Scam:** Often times, recruitment of staff is an important process in every institution. Staff are employed to handle certain responsibilities and also solidify the existing staff strength or replace outgoing staff because of retirement (Asiedu, 2011). It is natural to note that the process of recruiting staff is a transparent thing and in line with the current regulation contained in the organization's records. This ugly trend in the employment of staff in Nigeria's tertiary institutions explains the act of corruption. Others include bribing to have employment and recruitment of staff that are not effective. This is heightened by the high level of unemployment that is present in Nigeria as a country. In Nigeria, the basic thought that government jobs are better secured makes, people resort to anything within their reach to have government jobs. The

expenses in getting the new government employment can run into high amount of money which places the victims in distance years of struggling to clear the indebtedness.

7. Admission Racketeering: No tertiary institution can exist without the admission of students. In Nigerian, for quality education and quality graduates to be ensured, there is the need to strictly admit only qualified students into the tertiary institution. Admission of new students has come with so many issues. There has been issue of complete sales of slots for admission that goes for unimaginable large amount of money to students who are not qualified. This situation is also stressed with center men who deceive innocent candidates by putting them into outright deception, capitalizing on their situation with staff who are in-charge in the various institutions. There are also situations where individuals who are not even in the institution pretend to be official staff. This set of individuals increases the rate of racketeering infringement. Lawal (2018) exposes the corrupt act by highlighting that more cases of corruption practices in higher learning institutions where admission irregularities, racketeering and others were in full operation.

8. Student Intimidation: Anyone who is a student is a learner who is involved in the act of learning under the supervision of an instructor/teacher. A student is referred to as a pupil, an undergraduate, post-graduate or a scholar. A student is someone who attends a school and also search for knowledge from those experts that render teaching services from reading materials (n.d, 2019). A student is one that can access the various learning facilities in the school and beyond. He/she is directed, graded and promoted in line with the actual provision of the school.

The stipulated guiding rules for the students notwithstanding, lots of learners come under serious level of intimidation and rude harassment. Any time a staff (academic/nonacademic) through his position takes due advantage of the learner because of the situation of the student for his own personal gains, intimidation is in place. A reference point is when a staff issue a threat of failure to a female student may request from the student either sex or money for her to pass his course. Other examples include some lecturing staff subdue a student to a stage of slavery by turning him or her to errand servant without which, the student will fail his course. Some students turns to performing household chores function. Again, some associate Professors force students particularly post-graduate students to attending academic conferences and presenting papers for them. These post-graduate students cannot say no even if they have more important issues to attend to at the time. Some professors who teach large classes because of their ulterior motives end up forcing post-graduate students to mark students' examination scripts for them.

9. Theft: In Nigeria, the education sector includes early childhood, primary, secondary, and tertiary educational institutions, along with management structures, accreditation personnel, exam evaluation agencies and an act of licensing, inspection, and regulatory bodies (Kirya, 2019). It employs maximum numbers of staff, consumes enormous amounts of supplies, and requires a vast infrastructure. The sheer size of the sector makes it susceptible to corruption, given high amount of money allocated to it and the difficulty of supervision, inspection, and monitoring. Kirya further states that the tertiary institution is a victim of this major form of corruption where staff steal funds meant for major contracts. This happens in connection with some major officers in the schools. Others even claim that they were robbed when they are the culprits who are completely selfish. There are also situations of staff who steal funds put in their care for one ongoing contract or the other and cannot present same when it is needed and when the pressure is high, they end up absenting themselves. Corruption is as well seen as stealing of government assets by staff vested with such responsibilities. An extreme form is the high level of "spontaneous" privatization of government assets by greedy managers and some personnel who are in the transition process. Other indication about stealing involves: stealing of materials like office materials, cars, computers and accessories. The defaulters of dirty acts are always staff of middle class in their selfish interest, in some instances, for unsatisfactory salaries. Effective checks over assets are usually not effective. As an institution of higher learning, the ability to adopt justice and fairness in identifying and giving punishment to offenders should be put in place (Worldbank, 2016).

Corruption in Tertiary Institutions and the Effects

Every action has its effects, thus, corruption which is a current challenge in the tertiary institutions has its numerous effects. It is due to these effects that the system of education in Nigeria is on the fall. The tertiary institutions are finding it difficult to see the light of the day. The effects of corruption have been considered in several ways. Mgboji et al (2023) highlight on the effects of corruption in Nigerian tertiary institutions as follows:

1. Insufficient Funding

Tertiary institutions of learning should be effectively financed to support teaching and learning approaches, good research, modern studies and infrastructural improvement (Meier and Griffin, 2005). In line with Ololube (2007), the increasing level of corrupt practices in tertiary institutions of learning in Nigeria brings a big problem as stealing and wrong use of funds, assistance from private organizations and subventions from government authority results to insufficient finance for contracts when it is necessary.

2. Inadequate Development

There has been a noticeable reduction concerning the improvement of tertiary institutions as contracts which could have great influence to the majority of both workers and learners are left alone either intentionally or because of inadequate funding. There is an absolute insufficient main infrastructure and other facilities. The tertiary institution is considered literarily as a 'glorified secondary school'. All these are as a result of inadequate major infrastructural development for effective academic study. Dike (2003), in his submission notes that except the corruption and wrong application of funds are handled, there is bound to be so many malfunctional tertiary institutions.

3. Students Laziness

All the educational institutions of higher learning should proceed with effective operation, imbibing good rules and ensuring appropriate dignity in job implementation (Rinnert & Kobayashi, 2005). All these seem unattainable in the present time because of high level issues of sexual acts for grades, buying of scores and others which does not encourage committed students/learners from giving their best to serious studying. Students start looking, cutting corners that will seriously result to a bad reading habit thus resulting to manifesting unproductive and academically weak labour market.

4. Fallen Standard of Education

One of the greatest outcome of corruption in Nigeria's tertiary institutions of learning is the continuous collapse in the standard of education. This happens because of the kind of students that were admitted and the kind of unqualified workers that are given job appointments. This goes a long way to actually obstruct the overall productivity of the nation. The productivity of any nation is because of the graduates it turns out from the various tertiary institutions of learning.

5. Inadequate Effective Teachers

A teacher is someone who is the main working class in any tertiary institution. The teacher is expected to be a professional expert and effectively ready for the responsibility in the impartation of wisdom by encouraging the good product of student that are turned out into the society. The teachers are requested to be peculiar and should have desire for the profession of teaching. However, considering the level of corruption faced at the point of the effectiveness of teachers is a problem and this affects the quality of graduates released. Every responsible teacher will only impart into the students the knowledge he has and cannot give what he does not have (Darling-Hammond & Sykes, 2003).

6. Laxity on Integrity and Hard-Work

Another effect of corruption in tertiary institution of learning is that it does not encourage commitment and seriousness on the part of the staff and students since they rely on shortcuts to get rich or excellent scores. Learners who are committed to working hard see their colleagues who

are not responsible have good grades and they key into it by joining in the corrupt practices. Staff who are committed and hardworking notice that ineffective colleagues are living better than them and they easily join the moving train. (Amini-Philips & Ogbuagwu, 2017).

7. Poor Global Institution Rating

There are international bodies that are vested with the sole responsibility of rating tertiary institutions from the universal perspective. One of the international bodies is Webmetric and Times High Education. This organization has the function of annual rating of tertiary education considering the nature and quality of the researches that are carried out and the nature and quality of admission intakes. This is to ascertain their influence on the universal population (Khamala, Makosi & Nijraine, 2018). Khamala et al also state further that these rating bodies recognize the supports and what the tertiary institutions have contributed to the world development and research. Considering the nature of corruption that is badly affecting the pace of research work and institutional development, there is always a sharp reduction in rating percentages of various tertiary institutions of learning. Again, the required standard required from assessing the institutions are poor.

Tackling Corruption in Tertiary Institutions

The following are important while tackling corruption in tertiary institutions in Nigeria:

Human Tackling: So as to properly discourage corrupt practices, both the staff and students should take a decisive act in ensuring that the actual legitimate and justifiable things are done. They should make sure that the act of sticking to the just, truth and proper living are the practical and regular acts. The act of integrity should be upheld and practiced without stop (Hunja, 2015). Again, it is proper for persons in tertiary institutions to take an appropriate decision of not taking or giving bribe or practicing corruption. They should also sustain the fact that justice prevails without bias in the various institutions. Hunja (2015) also states how corruption can be tackled as soon as there is adequate reward for hard-work and excellence. Corrupt persons should be made known and justice should prevail because when the crime is protected, it results to further crime.

Institutional Tackling: So as effectively handle corrupt, every institution should ensure that effective rules which can check and destroy corrupt activities are put in place. In accordance with Whawo (2015), tertiary institutions of learning should check the workers and learners carefully and ensure adequate punishment to every category of defaulters. He also notes that both staff and students should be subjected to proper orientation on the evils of corruption and the manner in which it is bringing down the society. Tertiary institutions is expected to strictly employ staff who are proven and clean in character and respect into applicable and trusted positions that are sensitive. Again it is important for tertiary institutions to ensure that the uprising of technology to

automate every procedure so as to curtail man's interference and strengthen all-round cleanliness. In addition, tertiary institutions can support every act of bringing all wrong offenders to justice.

Societal Tackling: It is expected that every society should assume a proper position against its practices. Persons who have dangerous behaviour and/or questionable accumulation of material wealth have to be promptly and actually brought to justice if considered wanting (Karklins, 2005). In the same way every institution of higher learning in Nigeria should have a guiding principle that provides for every worker, the position notwithstanding, to declare assets both in assumption of office and leaving of office. Effective check should be conducted to be sure that there were no sign of packing or accruing corrupt wealth to self, friends, well wishers, colleagues, kinsmen or family members. The government is expected to put an end of celebrating corrupt personalities. Those persons, agencies and institutions that enforce law concerning corrupt practices should ensure justice by proper arrest, investigation and appropriate justice. Institutions and person should provide useful information about staff of questionable character. Relevant information that are needed to ensure the safety of institutional and societal core values should be at people disposals.

Conclusion

Tertiary institutions in Nigeria are the highest level of education. It includes universities, polytechnics and colleges. The tertiary institution is the last level of education that prepares the learner for effectiveness in the society. The tertiary institutions are however, badly affected by the effects of corruption.

The basic challenge in Nigerian Tertiary Institution is corruption. The effects of corruption has drastically reduced the expected standard of tertiary education in Nigeria. Tertiary education that is expected to breed excellent future leaders ends up producing ineffective leaders of tomorrow because of corruption. The disastrous effect of corruption in the nation's tertiary institution needs to be tackled from the perspective of human approach, organizational approach, societal approach and the likes.

Way Forward in Tackling Corruption

1. The government at the three levels of governance (the Local government level, State government level and the Federal government level) should effectively embrace the various anti-corruption programmes and initiatives.
2. The stakeholders should ensure proper and regular accountability in all levels of education on the nation to avoid the transfer of corruption from one level of education to another.

3. The government, curriculum planners and implementers should ensure that mainstream ethnic courses are enshrined into the tertiary education curriculum.
4. The government and other stakeholders should provide regular programmes and workshops on anti-corruption in the tertiary education sector for the staff and the students.
5. Every supervision in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria should have a supervisor.
6. Anti-corruption Agency should be established in all tertiary institution to check corruption practices.

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